

ІННОВАЦІЙНО-ІНВЕСТИЦІЙНА ПОЛІТИКА

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Principles, criteria and factors of implementation of innovative activity at enterprises of food industry

The subject of the research is the theoretical foundations of innovation as a promising area of business development in the food industry in Ukraine.

The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate the nature, types and principles of innovation and justify the prospects for its further development in Ukraine.

Research methods. The dialectical method of scientific cognition, analysis, method of comparison and generalization of data are used in the work.

Results of work. The article clarifies the essence, types, principles of innovation in the food industry in Ukraine. The directions of technological innovations by branches in the food industry are outlined. Emphasis is placed on the need to integrate different types of innovations that provide a synergistic effect. General and special principles of innovative development of the food industry are considered. Types of innovations in the development of food industry enterprises are characterized. The key factors influencing the innovative development of the food industry are identified. It is established that the creation of a modern model of management of innovative development of the food industry is possible through the introduction of new technological processes, the development of modern technologies, as well as partial or complete renewal of material and technical base.

Field of application. Innovation management.

Conclusions. The results of the study suggest that the successful implementation of innovations allows to ensure compliance with technical, environmental and social standards, increase economic efficiency and investment attractiveness of the food industry from the point of view of external investors.

Key words: innovations, innovative activity, innovative development, innovative activity, food industry,

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Принципи, критерії і фактори впровадження інноваційної діяльності на підприємствах харчової промисловості

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні засади інноваційної діяльності як перспективного напрямку розвитку бізнесу в харчовій промисловості в Україні.

Метою дослідження є теоретичне обґрунтування сутності, видів та принципів інноваційної діяльності та обґрунтування перспектив її подальшого розвитку в Україні.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, аналіз, метод порівняння та узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті з'ясовано сутність, види, принципи інноваційної діяльності на підприємствах харчової промисловості в Україні. Окреслено напрями технологічних інновацій за галузями у харчовій промисловості. Наголошено на необхідності інтеграції інновацій різного типу, що забезпечують синергетичний ефект. Розглянуто загальні та спеціальні принципи інноваційного розвитку харчової промисловості. Охарактеризовано види інновацій розвитку підприємств харчової промисловості. Визначено ключові чинники впливу на інноваційний розвиток підприємств харчової промисловості. Встановлено, що створення сучасної моделі управління інноваційним розвитком харчової промисловості можливе через впровадження нових технологічних процесів, освоєння сучасних технологій, а також часткове або повне оновлення матеріально–технічної бази.

Галузь застосування. Інноваційний менеджмент.

Висновки. Результати проведеного дослідження дають змогу стверджувати, що успішна реалізація інновацій дозволяє забезпечити відповідність продукції технічним, екологічним і соціальним стандартам, підвищити економічну ефективність та інвестиційну привабливість харчової промисловості з погляду зовнішнього інвестора.

Ключові слова: інновації, інноваційна діяльність, інноваційний розвиток, інноваційна активність, харчова промисловість.

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Принципы, критерии и факторы внедрения инновационной деятельности на предприятиях пищевой промышленности

Предметом исследования являются теоретические основы инновационной деятельности как перспективного направления развития бизнеса в пищевой промышленности в Украине.

Целью исследования является теоретическое обоснование сущности, видов и принципов инновационной деятельности и обоснование перспектив дальнейшего развития в Украине.

Способы исследования. В работе использован диалектический метод научного познания, анализ, метод сравнения и обобщения данных.

Результаты работы. В статье выяснены сущность, виды, принципы инновационной деятельности на предприятиях пищевой промышленности в Украине. Обозначены направления технологических инноваций по отраслям в пищевой промышленности. Отмечено необходимость интеграции инноваций разного типа, обеспечивающих синергетический эффект. Рассмотрены общие и особые принципы инновационного развития пищевой индустрии. Охарактеризованы виды инноваций развития предприятий пищевой промышленности. Определены ключевые факторы влияния на инновационное развитие предприятий пищевой промышленности. Установлено, что создание современной модели управления инновационным развитием пищевой промышленности возможно через внедрение новых технологических процессов, освоение современных технологий, а также частичное или полное обновление материально–технической базы.

Область применения. Инновационный менеджмент.

Выводы. Результаты проведенного исследования позволяют утверждать, что успешная реализация инноваций позволяет обеспечить соответствие продукции техническим, экологическим и социальным стандартам, повысить экономическую эффективность и инвестиционную привлекательность пищевой промышленности с точки зрения внешнего инвестора.

Ключевые слова: инновации, инновационная деятельность, инновационное развитие, инновационная активность, пищевая промышленность.

Formulation of the problem. The main goal of innovative development of the food industry is the process of improvement and systematic innovations aimed at significant improvements in all aspects of the food industry and based on the continuity of the search for new methods and means to meet consumer needs. The introduction of innovations includes the factor impact of market changes, including the risk of lack of demand for a new product, namely the probability of losses due to consumer rejection of the proposed product, ie the lack of a guaranteed market niche for its implementation. Innovative development of the food industry is the systematic and continuous implementation of food, technological, marketing and organizational innovations at all stages of food production, as a set of systemic and continuous measures, leads directly or indirectly to change the mechanism of the food industry in different conditions and situations. changes in order to achieve the goals of sustainable development.

Analysis of recent research and publications. A number of scientists are engaged in theoretical substantiation of the essence and directions of innovative activity in the food industry: V. Gubina [1], J. Deriy [2], A. Diskina [3], O. Kovalenko [5–6], S. Markova [9], I. Novoitenko [10], O. Rymar [13], O. Semenenko [14], S. Sukachova–Trunina [16], V. Khrypyuk [18] and others. At the same time, despite the work of various authors, some issues of innovative development in the food industry in Ukraine are still unresolved.

Setting objectives. The purpose of the article is to clarify the nature, types, principles of criteria and factors for the implementation of innovative activities in the food industry in Ukraine.

Presenting main material. At the present stage of functioning of the food industry of Ukraine there is no doubt about the need for the transition of the industry to an innovative model of economic development. Practice proves that it is innovative changes in the food industry that can improve the quality of domestic food, provide high rates of economic growth.

The need for innovation to ensure the development of the food industry is determined by current trends in society. The most significant factors influencing the intensity of innovation in activities include: the growing needs of society are forcing the food industry to form better, richer and more diverse products and offer more unified; Fierce com-

petition is a consequence of the transition of the food industry from aggressive price competition to competition in quality and optimal value for money, and also leads to the search and formation of new marketing strategies that allow deeper study of real consumer preferences to deepen market segmentation; general globalization leads to the diversification of production and the unification of different industries at the international and national levels. To maintain their position in such a situation, the food industry is forced to seek new management methods, new forms of cooperation, to unite in strategic alliances.

Representatives of most innovation theories emphasized that the nature of major socio-economic processes in society depends largely on the characteristics and dynamics of scientific and technological progress, and active innovation of economic entities forms an innovative type of development and contributes to its overall economic growth.

The Law of Ukraine «On Innovation» defines innovation as newly created (applied) and (or) improved competitive technologies, products, services, as well as organizational and technical solutions of industrial, administrative, commercial or other nature that significantly improve the structure and quality production and (or) social sphere [12].

In our opinion, to consider the concept of «innovation» as a result, rather than as a process for the food industry more effectively and thoroughly, because to define the concept of the process of creating innovation, there is the term «innovation». In economics, this concept appeared in the late 80's of the twentieth century and gained importance in scientific and technical, organizational and economic activities, which were carried out on the basis of scientific and technological progress and aimed at creating and implementing advanced technologies and techniques.

According to the Law of Ukraine «On Innovation», innovation is an activity aimed at using and commercializing the results of research and development and leads to the release on the market of new competitive goods and services [12].

A characteristic feature of economic growth based on innovation is that the achievement of individual industries is not due to factor costs, but mainly due to the introduction of new equipment and technologies. Their maintenance and organization of production requires a highly skilled work-

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force (both workers and management), which requires a higher appreciation of their work [4]. Due to the growth of household incomes, consumer demand for quality goods is increasing, and the internal competition of economic entities has a positive effect. The activity of scientific institutions, higher educational establishments, and infrastructural organizations is intensifying. National companies modernize and improve the technical parameters of equipment in order to increase the useful life or production capacity, create their own developments that help grow their competitive position in both national and foreign markets.

A special link is occupied by the food industry, as one of the leading sectors of the economy. The state of the economy, food security, development of internal and external markets, living standards depend on the level of its development and stability of functioning. The basis for the effective development of the food industry is the availability of raw materials, places of consumption of finished products, natural conditions, as well as scientific and technical potential.

Thus, the innovative development of the food industry is a process of improvement and system-

atic innovations aimed at significant improvements in all aspects of the food industry and is based on the continuity of the search for new methods and means to meet consumer needs.

The continuous implementation of innovative processes in the food industry together form a stream of potential change. The complex of changes that occur under the influence of innovation determines the pace and direction of development of the food industry. In order to increase the efficiency of industry development, this development must be continuous, this process can be ensured only through the constant inclusion of new elements that can act and various forms of innovation (Table 1).

Classification of innovations makes it possible to specify the directions of the innovation process, comprehensively assess its effectiveness, form economic mechanisms and organizational forms of innovation management, determine the means of innovation in the market, link to the type of innovation process, a particular innovation strategy.

The current international standards for collecting data on innovations apply, as already mentioned, only to technological innovations, cover new

Table 1. Classification of innovations in the food industry

The nature of innovation	Types of innovation processes
The level of novelty	Radical Ordinary
Stage of the product life cycle at which the innovation is introduced	Research and development in the food industry to create new and improve food Production (introduction of new, more modern technologies for manufacturing products).
Scope	Technological Production Economic Shopping Social In the field of management
According to the level of novelty	Local Sectoral National World
The pace of implementation	Fast Slow motion Those that are growing Uniform Jumping
The type of effect obtained as a result of the introduction of innovation	Economic Social Ecological Integral

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [1; 7]

products and processes, as well as their significant technological improvements [7].

The classification of innovations must take into account both the basic features of the objects of classification and the grouping of typological concepts by these features. In this case, each typological concept related to innovation is deepened by typological concepts from the relevant subgroups. For example, scientific and technical innovations are specified by the level of novelty (absolute, relative, conditional) or innovation potential (radical, combined). Each group has its own subgroups of basic features of classification. The peculiarity of grouping makes it possible to make appropriate management decisions on the feasibility of investing in the innovation process, the choice of methods of innovation development, risk assessment of both the innovation and forms of innovation process (Fig. 1) [7].

Therefore, innovations in the food industry should include those innovations that are accompanied by:

- restoration and development of food for consumers;

- qualitatively new changes in food;
- increasing the efficiency of the food industry infrastructure;
- збільшенням результативності управління стійким функціонування та розвитком харчової промисловості країни;
- increasing the efficiency of the processes of formation, positioning and consumption of food;
- strengthening the image of the food industry;
- progressive changes in factors of production.

According to the definition of areas of innovation, it is reasonable to assume that technological innovations are the most widely used in the food industry, their general difference is the cost and speed of implementation. It should be noted that the main requirement of almost all innovations in the food industry is the requirement to improve resource conservation, as well as environmental friendliness of the processes being implemented (Fig. 2).

In November 2008, the revision of the organizational and economic mechanism for the implementation of the common agricultural policy of the

Fig. 1. Classifier of innovations, innovation processes and innovations

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [7]

Fig. 2. Directions of technological innovations by branches in the food industry

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [10; 13]

European Union was completed, and in 2013 the next stage of reforming the common agricultural policy, adapting it to new long-term trends in the global agricultural sector. The European Commission has published a communication «Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) until 2020: Towards food, natural resources and territorial challenges of the future», which identified possible options for the development of the EU's common agricultural policy in 2013–2020 [11].

Innovative development of food industry enterprises is an integral part of the modern European agrarian country, so the main goal of the next reform of the common policy is the transition to a more dynamic, competitive and efficient agricultural sector of the economy.

Following public hearings, debates and conferences held by the European Commission in 2010, three main objectives for the future development of the common policy in the food sector were identified:

- viable food production (creation of safe and sufficient food stocks in the context of increased global demand, economic crisis and much higher market volatility, active participation in global food security);
- sustainable management of natural resources and climate change (farmers and farmers are often forced to prioritize environmental benefits over economic ones, and such costs are not bought in a free market);
- preserving the territorial balance and diversity of rural areas (the agricultural sector remains one of the main economic and social drivers in rural areas, an important tool for maintaining the quality of life in rural areas) [11].

Currently, the share of the food industry that innovates in total does not exceed 10%. The value of this indicator is four times lower than the corresponding target indicator of implementation of the Strategy of Innovative Development of Ukraine for 2010–2020 in the context of globalization challenges, which in turn leads to lack of effective mechanism for managing innovative development of food industry [15].

However, it should be emphasized the need to integrate different types of innovations that provide a synergistic effect. Thus, the development of fundamentally new products is often associated with the specifics of processing (technology) of the same type of raw material, while more fully takes into account the diversity of demand from different categories

of the population and provides deeper processing of raw materials. Marketing innovations promote faster distribution of the product with the possibility of its packaging and, at the same time, by increasing the shelf life, can increase its mass. The development of small-scale production and processing of agricultural raw materials in the food industry reduces losses, and in many cases improves product quality. Reasonable integration of various innovations will allow to modernize the food industry, provide import substitution and increase the level of management of innovative development of the food industry [1].

Thus, the innovative development of the food industry is the systematic and continuous implementation of food, technological, marketing and organizational innovations at all stages of food production in order to achieve the goals of sustainable development [1].

Sectoral features of investment processes set requirements that must be met by methods and tools for managing them in the long run [17].

In the table. 2 shows the principles of innovative development of the food industry.

All these principles are interrelated, which indicates the systematic application, ie non-compliance with one of the principles can lead to problems in the overall process of implementation and use of innovative processes in the food industry, and as a result, inefficient activities in general.

The modern economic literature offers many criteria by which the process of innovative development. Innovations are diverse in content and structure, in areas of application and scale of operation, in the nature of consumer properties, in the level of novelty and the nature of the consequences, and so on.

However, despite the fact that the classifications are made on a large number of different criteria, they do not contradict, but complement each other.

This is due to the very nature of innovations, their close relationship with each other, and the fact that the same innovation can be in different classification groups and even more than two, depending on the feature taken as a basis.

According to the source of innovation and the concept of food industry innovation, there are three types of innovation: from consumers, from the food industry, from specialized organizations. According to the degree of novelty of innovations, radical innovations can be distinguished, fundamentally new for the food industry market and modified (improving).

Table 2. Principles of innovative development of the food industry

Principle	Characteristics
GENERAL PRINCIPLES	
The principle of scientificity	Use of scientific knowledge and methods to implement innovations that meet the needs of consumers
The principle of systematicity	Taking into account all factors and conditions necessary to meet human needs in food, resource opportunities (economic, financial, environmental, etc.), social impact on society
The principle of safety	Innovations applied in the food industry must guarantee the absence of harm to the environment, man and his activities
The principle of feedback	Is the need to analyze the reaction of consumers to the implemented innovations. Innovation creates new needs, the maximum satisfaction of which is the global goal of the food industry. Thus, the new needs of consumers directly affect the formation of goals and objectives of the food sector
The principle of socio-economic adaptability	Provides for the process of mastering the food industry ways of functioning and development that meet the adequate conditions of the external environment, as well as contribute to improving the efficiency of the whole environment. Taking into account the constantly changing environmental factors, for example, in the field of legislation, science, economics, etc., determine the directions of innovative development of the food industry
The principle of complexity	Provides a comprehensive study of causal relationships, a comprehensive assessment of the input parameters of functional and structural structure, their change and development at the object in space and time, quantitative and qualitative characteristics and output parameters of this process
SPECIFIC PRINCIPLES	
The principle of interdependence	The innovation process ends with the appearance on the market of goods, which at a certain stage of its life cycle should cause the need (stimulate the idea) to create the next innovation and provide financial support for this process
The principle of sustainable development	The level of development of the food industry in the region directly depends on the level of development of the region and its resources. The greater the innovative opportunities of the region, the higher the level of innovative developments in the field of consumption
The principle of competitiveness	Determines the implementation of innovation activities taking into account the competitiveness of implemented innovations
The principle of controllability	Reflects the ability of innovative development to be subject to managerial influence at all stages
The principle of transparency	Allows to identify the degree of openness of the environment and characterizes the availability of a certain, clear and well-formed form of information necessary for making sound management decisions

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [7; 8; 10]

According to the form of ownership, it is advisable to classify innovations into state, municipal, private and collective.

According to the amount of investment capital required for the implementation of innovative development of the food industry, there are high-cost, medium-cost and low-cost innovations.

Depending on the difficulties of implementation of innovation processes, namely in the process of its creation and implementation, it is advisable to highlight the innovations developed by the food industry and external forces. If the innovation has complex characteristics for its implementation, as well as the necessary specific developments, materials, skills, relevant facilities, etc., the innovation process can be ordered from another party (country, organization, research institution, etc.) who have knowledge

and experience in this field. Such innovations include the development of a modern marketing strategy (logistics strategy, etc.) to promote food products in international markets or the creation of new automated food management systems.

The main types of innovations in the development of food industry enterprises, classified by content are presented in table. 3.

The implementation of the development of innovation processes in the food industry depends on many objective factors (Table 4).

Each of the groups of factors affects the innovative development of the food industry, but the degree of their impact is different. The general macroeconomic state of the state forms the conditions for the functioning of the industry as a whole and its innovative development.

Table 3. Types of innovations in the development of food industry enterprises by content

Kind of innovation	The content of innovation
Product innovations	Creation of new quality food products Improvement of already existing consumer foods Development of new types of raw materials and resources Attraction of new types of raw materials and resources Innovations in enterprises
Technological innovations	Use of information and communication technologies in the food industry Use of new technologies and techniques in the process of food production Development of new types of logistics Introduction of new forms of accounting and reporting Innovations in the system of transport and logistics services Greening of service technologies
Marketing innovations	Development of new segments of the food industry market Development of the latest models of food positioning and advertising
Organizational and managerial innovations	New forms and methods of food industry management Introduction of new information forms of territorial organization of food industry development Improving the process of public administration of innovative development of the food industry Involvement of public–private partnership Improvement of information support of the food industry
Service innovations	Introduction of new teaching methods, advanced training of food workers Development of innovative models of placement of labor resources in the food industry Development of innovative models of service of the food industry, taking into account the specifics of the location of productive forces

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [3; 7]

The state and development of the industry determine the possibilities of innovative development of the food industry, based on its domestic needs and available resources. That is, macro–level factors indirectly affect the innovative development of the food industry, and the meso–level and micro–level – directly.

Analysis of current areas of innovative development of the food industry allowed to group innovations that need to be implemented for sustainable development of the food industry (Table 5).

In terms of product innovations, the most relevant are the expansion of the range, in terms of technology – activities aimed at saving energy and raw materials, increasing the safe storage and implementation of waste–free production, marketing innovations – the use of environmentally friendly packaging and product awareness. Organizational innovations are related to improving the organization of business processes and should be aimed at creating the necessary conditions to ensure, realize innovation potential, improve economic ties, integrate the food industry with the agricultural sector, in particular, with farms, and create on their basis small enterprises [1].

For the effective implementation of innovative development it is necessary to organize and es-

tablish processes for the development of all types of innovation.

Such a management decision should be sufficient for the formation of strategic coordination and operational regulation of current activities. In general, the innovative development of food industry enterprises in Ukraine is characterized by instability, lack of balance of financial sources, lack of clearly defined priorities, which requires measures at the state level to promote its activation and optimization [7].

To intensify the innovative development of the food industry of Ukraine, we consider it necessary to take the following measures:

- increase the role of the state in the formation and support of innovative enterprises and their infrastructure, in particular, create a fund to promote small forms of innovative development with budget funds, provide benefits (tax, customs, tariff) for the initial stages of research and development of their results in production;

- to encourage food business entities to conduct scientific, technical and patent examination of innovative projects in compliance with internationally recognized norms and rules in order to minimize duplication and repeated or unjustified introduction into economic turnover;

Table 4. Factors influencing the innovative development of food industry enterprises

Factors	Factors hindering innovative development	Factors contributing to innovative development
1	2	3
Economic	Lack of funding sources High economic risk Lack of demand for products Low incomes Low integration of the food industry into the world economic system Reduction of demand for some types of food products	Availability of financial resources Development of competition in the food industry State financial support for innovative activities of the food industry High incomes High level of integration of the food industry into the world economic system The emergence of new consumer requirements for the quality of food products Development of public–private partnership
Technological	Weakness of material, technical and scientific base Outdated equipment and technology Low scientific and technical potential of enterprises, regions and the state	The emergence of the necessary scientific potential Availability of technical base Development of technology, the emergence of new technologies in the food industry and related industries
Organizational and managerial	Stable organizational structures Excessive centralization Lack of innovation strategy Indifference of managers to innovations The complexity of reconciling the interests of participants in innovation processes Lack of international cooperation	Flexibility of organizational structures Democratic style of government Formation of creative target groups Decentralization Qualified marketing International scientific and technical cooperation New forms of cooperation Creation of innovation infrastructure
Legal	Imperfection of the legislative framework on innovation and industry Imperfection of the legal framework on intellectual property Violation in all its manifestations of the existing legislation of Ukraine	Legislative measures (benefits, laws) that encourage innovation Support for the development of the food industry by the authorities Development of the state concept of food industry development
Political	Political instability Criminogenic circumstances Force majeure: environmental, man–made disasters, terrorist acts	Political stability Minimization of the level of criminal environment
Socio–psychological	Resistance to change Fear of uncertainty Low professional status of the innovator Lack of material incentives and conditions for creative work Outflow of scientific personnel Low level of wages	Susceptibility to change, innovation Moral and material reward The possibility of self–realization Favorable psychological climate in the team Development of conditions of creative work High level of wages
Information and communication	Insufficient information about innovations, sources of their development and dissemination Insufficient information exchange for innovation management Closed and limited inter–branch relations Lack of sufficient protection of all types of property of information resources	The ability to quickly obtain the necessary information The right choice of information channels Acquisition of licenses, patents, know–how Constant replenishment of the information fund of the food industry Expansion of horizontal information flows
Integration	Non–compliance of national norms with the norms of the European Union	Faster and more effective realization of Ukraine’s national interests in multilateral cooperation of states

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [7]

Table 5. Directions of innovative development of the food industry

Type of innovation	Direction of innovative development
Food	Development of new technologies for the production of «healthy food» products Production of semi–finished products and products that require minimal processing Development of products for special groups, children, people with disabilities Production of organically pure products
Technological	Introduction of waste–free production Application of energy–saving and resource–saving technologies at all stages of production and storage of products Increasing the shelf life of products using packaging materials with fungicidal properties
Marketing	Use of biodegradable packaging Creating edible packaging Development of modern technologies of marketing, advertising and product promotion
Organizational	Application of modern quality control and certification systems Creating a mechanism for interaction between producers and stakeholders in the production and sale of food Active development of small business Constant increase of innovative activity of workers
Political	Compliance with the implementation of the Agreement with the European Union

Source: compiled by the author on the basis [13]

– to develop and implement a system of information support for innovative development with coverage of the results of the main trends in the development of domestic and foreign food markets, taking into account the requirements and needs of consumers;

– to improve statistical monitoring of innovative development of the food industry, to develop and implement a methodological apparatus for assessing the level of innovative development of the industry as a whole and by individual activities, to optimize the system of national statistical reporting and ensure its adaptation to EU standards.

Conclusions

Sustainable development of society involves increasing economic, social and environmental efficiency, which is becoming especially important for the food industry of Ukraine. Innovative activity of the industry provides the production of modern types of food, the development of new types and forms of storage, forms of promotion of finished products to different groups. The creation of a modern model of management of innovative development of the food industry is possible through the introduction of new technological processes, the development of modern technologies, as well as partial or complete renewal of material and technical base. A characteristic feature of innovation processes is the ability to withstand macroeconomic changes and external pressures. Successful implementation of innova-

tions allows to ensure compliance of products with technical, environmental and social standards, increase economic efficiency and investment attractiveness of the industry from the point of view of an external investor.

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